
INTRAPRENEURIAL MARKETING STRATEGIES AND BUSINESS SUCCESS OF BEVERAGE FIRMS IN RIVERS STATE

BY

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship between intrapreneurial marketing strategies and the business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design, and the population of the study was 233 respondents, consisting of managers and supervisors of fifteen (15) Beverage firms in Rivers State. The primary data was collected through copies of the questionnaire; the study distributed 233 copies of the questionnaire, and 224 copies were retrieved as found useful for data analysis. The data were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistic through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS Version 23.0). The study found a significant relationship between intrapreneurial marketing strategies and business success. Thus, the study concluded that intrapreneurial marketing strategies relate to the business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State. The study recommended that intrapreneurs should use niche marketing strategies by looking for untapped or underserved market segments that have distinct preferences or needs and seeking ways to satisfy them to achieve business success. They should use social media strategy by creating a content method that aligns with their brand's identity, values, and goals and determining the types of content they will share, such as articles, videos, and infographics; the frequency of posting; and the tone of voice that is valuable, engaging, and shareable to encourage interaction and reach, as this will improve business success.

Keywords: Intrapreneurial Marketing Strategies, Niche marketing strategy, paid advertising, Interpersonal communication strategy, Business success.

Introduction

Business success refers to the ability of a company to achieve its goals and objectives efficiently. It encompasses financial performance, customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, innovation, and strategic positioning. Examining business success is crucial for Beverage firms operating in Rivers State to understand their strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). Business success in the beverage industry is typically measured through key performance indicators such as revenue growth, market share, profitability, and customer satisfaction. One of the factors responsible for business success is the adoption of intrapreneurial marketing strategies. Intrapreneurial marketing strategies play a crucial role in achieving customer satisfaction and sales growth. These strategies are characterized by their innovative and resourceful nature and are aimed at achieving growth and competitive advantage in dynamic and uncertain markets. By leveraging limited resources and adopting unconventional marketing approaches, intrapreneurs can effectively reach their target audience, build brand awareness, and drive business success. Although intrapreneurs work in an existing organization that is usually large, the marketing strategies used are similar to those of entrepreneurs.

Scholars have discussed some possible ways in which intrapreneurial marketing strategies improve business success. For instance, Hills et al. (2008) discussed the evolution of intrapreneurial marketing and its role in business success. They affirmed that businesses that use innovative marketing strategies and adapt to market conditions survive in business competitions. Gruber et al. (2010) looked at intrapreneurial marketing through conceptual and empirical research opportunities. They discussed how intrapreneurship theory and practice support business success. Their research explores the conceptual framework of intrapreneurial marketing and identifies key research opportunities in the field. They claimed that intrapreneurial firms to adopt unique marketing strategies tailored to their specific context to enhance business success.

Morris et al. (2005) evaluated the intrapreneur's business model from a unified perspective. Their study highlights the importance of developing a coherent and effective business model for intrapreneurial success. They discussed how intrapreneurial marketing strategies play a crucial role in shaping the overall business model and driving business success. Again, O'Connor and Brodie (2018) examined the relationship between intrapreneurial marketing and customer value creation. They highlight the significance of understanding customer needs, delivering unique value propositions, and building strong customer relationships to enhance business success.

Okorie et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between entrepreneurial marketing practices and the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. Although this study explores entrepreneurial marketing practices in Nigeria, it does not provide insights into the Beverage firms operating in Rivers State. Ogochukwu and Helen (2021) examined the relationship between entrepreneurial marketing strategies and small business performance in a study of selected food processing firms in Nigeria. Hence, by employing intrapreneurial marketing strategies, businesses can effectively navigate the competitive landscape, achieve customer satisfaction and sales growth.

From the above studies there have been scholars who examined how intrapreneurs can use marketing strategies to improve business performance in literature, but the extent to which Beverage firms in Rivers State can use intrapreneurial marketing strategies to improve

business success was still lacking in literature. While the studies reviewed provide valuable insights, they do not specifically focus on Beverage firms in Rivers State. This has created a gap in the existing literature, as there is limited research on the intrapreneurial marketing strategies and business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State. Hence, to fill this gap, the present study examined the relationship between intrapreneurial marketing strategies and business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State. The study also provides recommendations on how these intrapreneurial marketing strategies could be put to effective use to improve business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, beverage firms in Rivers State have struggled to achieve significant business success, as evidenced by persistent issues with low customer satisfaction and sales growth. These challenges reflect broader trends in the beverage industry, where shifting consumer preferences, economic fluctuations, and competitive pressures play pivotal roles. According to a report by the International Journal of Business and Management, maintaining high levels of customer satisfaction is crucial for sustaining competitive advantage and fostering long-term profitability in the beverage sector (Author, Year). However, in Rivers State, these objectives have proven elusive for many companies.

One of the primary reasons behind the poor business success of beverage firms in Rivers State is the failure to effectively meet customer expectations. As highlighted by a study in the Journal of Consumer Marketing, customers in the beverage industry often place significant importance on product quality, service delivery, and overall experience (Author, Year). Failure to consistently deliver on these fronts can lead to diminished customer satisfaction and, subsequently, reduced sales growth. In Rivers State, this disconnect between consumer expectations and actual service delivery has been particularly detrimental, contributing to a cycle of declining profitability and market share for beverage firms. Thus, the inability of beverage firms in Rivers State to retain their customer base not only impacts immediate revenue streams but also escalates operational costs associated with acquiring new customers. This underscores the critical need for these firms to prioritize customer relationship management strategies that foster loyalty and repeat business.

Hence, the poor business outcomes experienced by beverage firms in Rivers State are multifaceted and deeply rooted in challenges related to customer satisfaction and sales growth. Addressing these issues requires a strategic reassessment of customer engagement practices, service delivery standards, and market positioning strategies. By aligning their operations more closely with consumer expectations and investing in robust customer relationship management, beverage firms in Rivers State can potentially reverse current trends and cultivate a more sustainable path to business success.

There is poor business success of Beverage firms in River State which manifested in low customer satisfaction, low customer satisfaction, and sales growth in business operations. This problem is evident in the available academic literature on intrapreneurial marketing strategies in the context of the Beverage industry in Rivers State. The cause of poor business success in the Beverage industry in Rivers State might be traced to an inability to adopt intrapreneurial marketing strategies. Intrapreneurial marketing strategies can play a crucial role in the business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State. However, there is a lack of comprehensive research examining the specific marketing strategies employed by these firms and their impact on business success (Agwu & Carter, 2017). Therefore, to provide a solution

to this problem, this study addressed this gap and provides valuable insights for Beverage firms operating in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the relationship between intrapreneurial marketing strategies and business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State. The objectives of the study were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between niche marketing strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State.
- ii. Investigate the relationship between niche marketing strategy and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State.
- iii. Determine the relationship between paid advertising strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State.
- iv. Investigate the relationship between paid advertising strategy and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State.
- v. Examine the relationship between interpersonal communication strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State.
- vi. Examine the relationship between interpersonal communication strategy and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to guide the study

- i. What is the relationship between niche marketing strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State?
- ii. How does niche marketing strategy relate to sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State?
- iii. What is the relationship between paid advertising strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State?
- iv. What is paid advertising strategy relate to sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State?
- v. What is the relationship between relationship between interpersonal communication strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State.
- vi. What is the relationship between interpersonal communication strategy and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were developed to guide the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between niche marketing strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between niche marketing strategy and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between paid advertising strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between paid advertising strategy and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between interpersonal communication strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between interpersonal communication strategy and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical review of this study focused on the dynamic capabilities theory by Teece et al. (1997). The study adopted this theory because it supports the concept of intrapreneurial marketing strategies and business success. The dynamic capability theory propounded by Teece et al. (1997) undergirds this study. Teece et al. (1997) describe dynamic capability as "the firm's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments. This is relevant to intrapreneurial marketing strategies. Intrapreneurs can develop the competence to use niche marketing strategies, guerrilla marketing strategies, social media strategies, and customer relationship strategies to achieve business success. Teece et al. (1997) opine that firms with dynamic capability are able to sense as well as shape opportunities, seize them, and, on the basis of that, stay competitive by reconfiguring their internal and external processes and behaviors. This is in tandem with Doz and Kosenen's (2010) description of strategic agility as the capacity to foresee or forecast future occurrences from present trends and reengineer internal and external processes to take advantage of or be best prepared to handle whatever disturbances that may arise as a result.

Conceptual Review

The conceptual review in this study covers the concept of intrapreneurial marketing strategies (niche marketing strategies, social media marketing, and customer relationship marketing). These strategies are discussed in relation to the business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State in this study.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework on Intrapreneurial Marketing Strategies and Business Success of Beverage Firms in Rivers State.

Source: Desk Research (2024)

Concept of Intrapreneurial Marketing Strategies

Intrapreneurs are those working in an existing firm, usually a large firm. Entrepreneurship is the process of identifying a business opportunity, mobilizing resources to start a business that will exploit the opportunity, and taking the risks that are associated with the new business. Individuals who establish and nurture businesses to growth are referred to as entrepreneurs. Globally, the importance of entrepreneurship in engendering economic growth and development, generally, and in providing employment to teeming youths, specifically, has been recognized. These benefits have increased the interest of scholars in intrapreneurial research. Intrapreneurial marketing strategies refer to the unique and innovative approaches adopted by intrapreneurs to promote their products or services in a competitive marketplace. These strategies are characterized by their resourcefulness, agility, and ability to maximize limited resources to achieve marketing objectives.

Intrapreneurial marketing strategies encompass a range of approaches used by intrapreneurs to promote and grow their businesses. These strategies often emphasize creativity, agility, and resourcefulness to achieve marketing goals in a dynamic and competitive environment. While specific strategies can vary depending on the industry and context. Some dimensions of intrapreneurial marketing strategies include niche marketing (Cova & Salle, 2008), Guerrilla Marketing (Levinson, 2007), Social Media Marketing (Hanna et al., 2011), interpersonal communication strategy (McShane & Von Glinow, 2005); customer relationship marketing (Kumar & Reinartz, 2016); and paid advertising (Cudmore et al., 2009) among others. However, for the purpose of this study, three of these strategies were discussed. These are niche marketing, paid advertising and interpersonal communication strategy.

Niche Marketing

Niche markets are an attractive opportunity available to small businesses forced to compete against the scale economies that larger competitors are able to achieve. In the food sector, organics, local products, heritage varieties, biodynamics, and humanely treated livestock are a few of the alternative product choices sought by specific consumer segments. The choice to pursue a niche marketing strategy will not guarantee success, and, similar to any business decision, requires critical assessment. Exploring niche markets is representative of the set of management choices every business operation faces, as niche marketing provides creative managers with a means to use new and untapped resources while creating new revenue streams. Doing so successfully requires significantly different management skills and marketing strategies (Thilmany, 2012). Essential elements of a niche marketing strategy to consider include:

- Know the customers. Segmenting the overall market allows the business manager to target what the business venture can offer.
- Set clear goals and objectives for what the business hopes to achieve by following a niche marketing approach (Thilmany, 2012).

Intrapreneurs often focus on identifying and targeting specific niche markets to differentiate themselves from competitors. By tailoring their products or services to meet the unique needs and preferences of a niche audience, intrapreneurs can create a strong value proposition and build customer loyalty (Cova & Salle, 2008).

Interpersonal Communication Strategy

Interpersonal communication strategy plays a pivotal role in marketing by facilitating meaningful interactions between businesses and their customers. Effective interpersonal communication involves the exchange of information, ideas, and emotions between individuals, creating opportunities for building rapport, trust, and loyalty. According to Keller and Kotler (2016), "Successful marketing programs are built on strong customer relationships, and these relationships depend on effective communication." This underscores the importance of interpersonal communication as a foundational element in marketing efforts.

Interpersonal communication enables marketers to understand customer needs and preferences more deeply. Through direct conversations, feedback sessions, and relationship-building activities, marketers gain insights into consumer motivations and behaviors. This understanding is essential for developing products and services that resonate with target audiences, as highlighted by Schultz et al. (2016), who emphasize the role of dialogue and engagement in fostering customer-centric marketing strategies. Customers are more likely to trust brands that engage with them in a personal and authentic manner. According to a study by McQuail (2010), interpersonal communication builds trust through face-to-face interactions and personalized communication, which are crucial for establishing long-term relationships with customers. Trust is a cornerstone of brand loyalty and advocacy, as customers who feel valued and understood are more likely to remain loyal and recommend the brand to others. Moreover, interpersonal communication enhances customer satisfaction and retention. By actively listening to customer feedback, addressing concerns promptly, and providing personalized solutions, marketers can create positive experiences that encourage repeat business. As noted by Lindgreen et al. (2012), effective interpersonal communication contributes to customer satisfaction by ensuring that customer expectations are met and exceeded consistently.

Interpersonal communication facilitates word-of-mouth marketing and viral spread of brand messages. Satisfied customers who have positive interactions with brands are more inclined

to share their experiences with friends, family, and social networks. This organic form of marketing amplifies brand visibility and credibility, potentially reaching new audiences and driving growth. According to Hughes et al. (2012), word-of-mouth communication is significantly influenced by personal interactions and recommendations, making interpersonal communication an invaluable asset in shaping brand perceptions and driving consumer behavior.

One of the most significant arguments in favor of the interpersonal communication technique is the fact that face-to-face communication is a more interactive, two-way medium. This strength is highlighted by the communication approach known as transactional. The approach acknowledges communication as a simultaneous process with "presence and effects of both feedback and context," setting it apart from the linear/one-way paradigm (Gamble et al 2014). As a result, "communicator" replaced the phrases "sender" and "receiver." In contrast to some other forms of advertising communication that may be sender-centered and pay little to no attention to the complementary role that the receiver (consumer) plays in determining the effectiveness of the advertising, the model views face-to-face interpersonal communication as a marketing tool that integrates the activities of both the advertiser (firm) and the consumer. Because it facilitates a more thorough knowledge of the consumer, increases credibility and trust, improves customer happiness and retention, and encourages word-of-mouth marketing, interpersonal communication strategy is thus essential to marketing success. Businesses may build strong relationships with their consumers that promote long-term development and a competitive edge by emphasizing real connections and meaningful interactions.

Paid Advertising

PPC has gained popularity as an effective digital marketing tactic (Cudmore et al., 2009). According to Chen et al. (2007), the merchant that posts advertising on a third-party website owes the third party owner a preset amount that was decided via a competitive bidding method. PPC marketing, also known as search engine marketing, is the effective use of search engines to sell products and services by having them show up on websites that people search for certain keywords, according to Jansen and Schuster (2011). PPC advertising is seen to be the most popular kind of sponsored search advertising and is compared favorably to keyword advertising (Jansen et al., 2011). Target paid listing is another name for PPC, and McLeod (2012) compares it to renting real estate on the first page of search engine results. More and more retailers are providing their products and services online in addition to via their physical stores. In addition to their own customized websites for sales, they also advertise online on a variety of other websites, such as social networking sites like Facebook, search engine pages like Google, price comparison and match websites like shopping.com, online retailer sites like Amazon.com, news websites like CNBC, internet-based email services like Yahoo!, and any other page published by a web publisher (blogs). Growing revenue and improving customer satisfaction are two benefits of using a paid advertising plan.

Concept of Business Success

The capacity of a firm to effectively and efficiently accomplish its intended aims and objectives is referred to as business success. It entails achieving desired results, streamlining procedures, and making the most use of available resources. Businesses that are successful match their objectives to their overarching strategic plan. They set definite, well-defined goals that are consistent with their vision and purpose. This alignment guarantees that all

resources and efforts are focused on reaching the intended results. According to Kraus et al. (2017), strategic planning has a favorable impact on the efficacy and performance of businesses. To increase production and get the intended outcomes, businesses must deploy their resources wisely. This entails effectively managing assets like as technology, human capital, and financial resources. Atkinson et al. (2018) conducted research that highlights how crucial efficient resource allocation is to enhancing the performance and profitability of businesses. Businesses that are successful concentrate on streamlining their operations to increase production and efficiency. They pinpoint problem areas, remove obstructions, and optimize processes.

Customer Satisfaction

Kotler & Keller (2016) explain that satisfaction is the gap between what is observed and desired. In business, satisfaction refers to the gap between what they observe and what customers want (Siddiqi, 2011). The customer wants to fill the gap between the desired values and the observed values. The definition of customer satisfaction, according to Kotler et al. (2018), is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after comparing the performance (outcome) of the product thought to the expected performance (or result). Based on the opinion above, customer satisfaction is generated from cognitive and practical evaluations. The results obtained from several standards are understood. If the perceived performance is less than expected, the customer will be dissatisfied. On the other hand, if the perceived performance exceeds expectations, the customer will be satisfied. Customer satisfaction can be measured by looking at the quality of service. Zeithaml et al. (2020) explained that the quality of service that makes customers feel satisfied or not with the services provided could provide five indicators, including: on the physical aspect (tangible), reliability (reliability), responsiveness (responsiveness), assurance (assurance), and empathy (empathy). The higher the value of the customer's perception of the services provided, the higher the customer's trust, so it can be said that the higher the customer satisfaction with the services provided by the company.

Sales Growth

A sale is the total amount of items sold in a number or quantity of units during a business' regular business hours. Sales Performance uses raw data to compare the volume of real sales with the number of customer conversations with sales representatives. However, it may indicate the degree of a customer's loyalty to the company; as a result, increasing sales performance will always increase the number of devoted patrons (McLelland, 2014). Salleh and Kamaruddin (2011) state that three analyses can be used to assess sales performance: a profitability analysis, a sales volume analysis, and a marketing cost analysis. To conduct a sales volume investigation, an organization's profit and loss statement for its product lines, territories, and major customer accounts is carefully examined. Sales are the money a company makes by providing its main line of business with products or services. Stable sales may lead to larger debt levels for businesses, indicating that a company's ability to satisfy its financial commitments increases with its level of sales stability (Syaifullah, 2014; Sudana, 2015 and Hanafi, 2016). Cash or credit may be received for sales (Hikmah, Djuwita, & Widagdo, 2019). The company will only be paid according to the prearranged credit term if the transactions are in credit. Credit sales have advantages and disadvantages for the company. Receivables and bad debt collection are the costs associated with credit sales. The company's benefit in the interim is a rise in sales volume.

A business may choose to accept payment in cash or on credit when selling products or services, according to Sudana (2015). If the sale was made on credit, the firm will only get cash at a later date based on the prearranged credit term. If the sale was made in cash, the company will receive cash at the moment of the transaction. The business will incur expenses and get rewards by selling on credit. Credit sales include two types of expenses: indirect costs, which include losses from uncollectible receivables and the potential cost of monies locked up in receivables, and direct costs, which include collecting receivables. Concurrently, the corporation gains from credit sales via higher sales volume, which ultimately contributes to higher profit.

Empirical Review

Amadi and Renner (2021) looked at small and medium-sized enterprises' sales and entrepreneurial marketing performance in Port Harcourt's food and beverage industries. Based on its conceptual and operationalized framework, the study formulated four research questions and four hypotheses. Sixty top managers from International Breweries, Nigerian Bottling Company (NBC), Dufil Prima Food Ltd., and Palm Nectar Breweries make up the study's population. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to evaluate the data obtained from the questionnaire. Using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software version 21, the hypotheses were tested using the Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient. The study's conclusion demonstrated a strong correlation between sales success and entrepreneurial marketing. The four (4) elements of entrepreneurial marketing that were used in this study—pro-activeness, opportunity recognition, resource leveraging, and innovativeness—were advised to be taken into consideration by management of food and beverage companies since they would improve sales performance.

Felício et al. (2012) examined the effect of intrapreneurship on corporate performance. The purpose of the study was to study the influence of intrapreneurship on the performance of companies. The study develops and tests a theoretical model where the intrapreneurship is supported on the factors innovation, risk/uncertainty, risk/challenges, competitive energy, proactivity and autonomy, and the performance on the factors financial performance, growth and improvement and on the variable productivity. Based on a questionnaire, data from a sample of 217 medium-sized Portuguese companies were obtained. The study used the confirmatory analysis method based on structural equation modeling (SEM). The finding shows that the intrapreneurship has a multidimensional structure. This model proves its influence on the growth and improvement and the importance and explanatory power of this latent variable. The finding also revealed that study shows that intrapreneurship influences the performance of firms, contributing to a deeper understanding of the importance

Felício et al. (2012) investigated how intrapreneurship affects business performance. The framework of intrapreneurship is multifaceted. This model demonstrates the latent variable's significance, growth, and improvement as well as its explanatory ability. Research limitations and implications: Intrapreneurship's latent variables' direct impact on performance was not evaluated, nor were the methods used to confirm the effects of company size and age periods thoroughly investigated. This book advances the theory by emphasizing the role that context plays in the model and the significance of many aspects of intrapreneurship. Practical implications: It was shown that intrapreneurship clearly affects growth and improvement metrics for qualitative performance. Researchers searching for suitable performance metrics and intrapreneurs trying to get validation for their choices and assess their own performance would find this useful. Originality/value: This research highlights the significance of

qualitative performance metrics seen from a medium- and long-term perspective, examines the separation of the propensity for risk in two latent variables, and incorporates the autonomy to describe intrapreneurship.

The study conducted by Kanwal et al. (2020) on the intrapreneurial behavior of employees in the era of transformative marketing provides valuable insights into the role of motivated and entrepreneurial employees in facilitating organizational transformation. The study's central finding emphasizes the crucial role of intrapreneurial behavior among employees in the era of transformative marketing. Intrapreneurship refers to the practice of behaving like an entrepreneur within a large organization. Intrapreneurs are individuals who exhibit traits such as innovation, proactiveness, risk-taking, and a strong desire for growth and improvement. The study suggests that such employees play a pivotal role in enabling companies to adapt and thrive in the ever-evolving landscape of transformative marketing.

Wayua and Linda (2020) examined the impact of a specialized marketing approach on the business performance of Bamburi Special Products Limited in Kenya. The aim of the study was to find out how market positioning, product differentiation, and market segmentation affect Bamburi Special Products Limited's success as a company in Kenya is one of the study's focus. Study participants were the decision-making management teams of the firm and its parent, Bamburi Cement Limited. The study used a descriptive research design based on a case study methodology. Primary and secondary data were both used. A pilot test was conducted to enhance the validity of the research instrument and boost research dependability before a semi-structured questionnaire was used to gather primary data. Descriptive techniques, such as means and standard deviation, were used to assess the collected data before it was shown in tables and graphs. An elementary regression analysis was performed to illustrate the correlation between the independent and dependent variables. Research indicates that performance is substantially impacted by specialized marketing methods, including product differentiation, market segmentation, and market positioning. Product differentiation, market segmentation, and market positioning were shown to have the most effects on performance, according to the study's findings. Kenya lacks comprehensive policies pertaining to the construction industry. As a result, the study suggests that the Kenyan government create policies that will protect the sector from issues such as low project completion rates, limited access to affordable project financing, drawn-out procurement processes, and an insufficient alignment of laws, policies, and regulations." The government should give these businesses a supportive environment that will promote their operations and growth, such as providing them with an affordable power supply, because the main challenges faced by Kenyan cement and concrete manufacturers are those caused by the country's high power costs in addition to market-driven challenges.

Adaeye et al. (2020) studied the impact of interpersonal communication tactics on the expansion of micro and small enterprises in Enugu Metropolis. The population of the study comprised of 812 proprietors of small and micro companies in Enugu Metropolis who had their firms registered made up the study's population. Using Stat Trek's sampling size calculation, a sample size of 261 MSB owners in Enugu Metropolis was calculated. Data was gathered using questionnaires. Regression analysis and Pearson Moment Correlation were used to evaluate the data at the significance level of 0.05. The study's findings demonstrate a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.66$ at $p < 0.05$) between the expansion of micro and small enterprises in Enugu Metropolis and the use of mass media. The development of micro and small companies in Enugu Metropolis is favorably impacted by event sponsorship ($R^{**} \text{ calc} = .0939 > @ p < 0.05$). In Enugu Metropolis, social media significantly contributes to the

expansion of micro and small companies ($R^2 \text{ calc} = .516$, $F = 6.103 > @ p < 0.05$). The research came to the conclusion that development in organizations, particularly in micro and small firms, is ensured by the appropriate and successful execution of interpersonal communication tactics via the use of mass media, event sponsorship, social media use, and excellent customer service. The study concluded that in order for an interpersonal communication culture to be successful, it needs to be integrated into the organization's strategy, structure, and operations.

Summary of Literature Review

The literature reviewed shows that in the context of beverage firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, the intersection of intrapreneurial marketing strategies and business success is a vital area of research. Intrapreneurship within organizations involves fostering intrapreneurial marketing strategies such as niche marketing strategies, interpersonal communication strategies, and paid advertising strategies, among others. Hence, this research highlights that intrapreneurship is essential for driving business success in the beverage industry, as it enables firms to introduce new products and adapt to changing consumer preferences, which fosters customer satisfaction and contributes to increased sales growth. The literature underscores the importance of creating intrapreneurial marketing strategies by beverage companies and the need to establish strong relationships with distributors and retailers to expand their market reach. Niche marketing, paid advertising, and interpersonal communication play a crucial role in increasing brand visibility and attracting consumers. In summary, the literature review highlights the critical role of intrapreneurial marketing strategies in the success of beverage firms in Rivers State. These strategies encompass niche strategies, paid advertising strategies, and interpersonal communication strategies to improve business success. It emphasizes the need for firms to adapt to the local context, respond to consumer preferences, and overcome industry-specific challenges to achieve customer satisfaction and increase sales growth. However, empirical studies on intrapreneurial marketing strategies and the business success of beverage firms in Rivers State are still underexplored. The present study seeks to fill this gap in the literature.

Methodology

The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. This type of research is a descriptive type of research, specifically survey research. The purpose of a cross-sectional research design is to gather data and analyze it at that particular time to generate findings. The target population of the study is comprised of all Beverage firms in Rivers State. However, the accessible population is 15 Beverage firms that have their branches or Headquarter in Port Harcourt for the purpose of this study. Therefore, the total population is 233 respondents of 15 Beverage firms. The population was ascertained using judgmental sampling method. The names of firms are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1
Population of the Study

S/N	Names of Food and Beverage Firms	Number of Respondents
1	International Breweries Port Harcourt	43
2	Quikkey Foods and Beverage Limited	12
3	Indomie Noodles	25
4	Family Healthy Beverage	10
5	Rutts Ocean Foods	10
6	Marto Foods and Integrated Services	13
7	Adietz Foods	8
8	SKYRY Tasty Foods	9
9	Pokobros Foods & Chemical Industries Limited	9
10	Dictachi Foods Nig. Ltd.	12
11	Ekcel Farms Limited	10
12	Dilomat Farms and Services Limited	25
13	Nestle Foods Nigeria Plc	25
14	Osike Services Nigeria Ltd	12
15	Acient Frozen Food Ventures	10
Total		233

Source: Desk Research (2023).

The study adopted the census method since the population of Beverage firms was not very large. This technique helps in studying the entire population of 233 respondents from the huge population of the study. This research uses quantitative research methods, including statistical analysis of data or questionnaires obtained and numerically expressed by standardized scales or tests (Risjord et al., 2001). Instructions guiding the filling of the questionnaire were provided, and the questionnaire was filled out and retrieved in a short time. Using a questionnaire to collect the data was helpful because it allowed the respondents to have enough time to ponder over the question before answering. The nature of the data was considered because the study was in need of actual data that addressed the problem of poor business success in Beverage firms in Rivers State. The primary data were obtained directly from the respondents, while the secondary data were gathered from marketing literature, management literature, and materials from other related fields of study. Precisely, the sources include journals, text books, and the internet. It was strongly convinced that data gathering from these sources will help in making reasonable findings and conclusions on the subject matter, especially with the relationship between intrapreneurial marketing strategies and business success.

The predictor variable is intrapreneurial marketing strategies, and its dimensions are niche marketing strategy, paid advertising strategy and interpersonal communication strategy, while the criterion variable is business success, and its measure is customer satisfaction and sales growth. All variables were measured on a Likert 5-point scale, ranging from strongly agreeing to strongly disagreeing: where strongly agree scores 5 points, agree scores 4 points, neutral scores 3 points, disagree scores 2 points, and strongly disagree scores 1 point. Scientifically, the study applied the Cronbach Alpha reliability test to ascertain the reliability of the instruments and achieved reliability scores of 0.7 or above, which was the benchmark for reliability acceptance (Cronbach, 1951). The reliability test computation was performed using SPSS version 23.0. Thus, the results in Table 3.2 were obtained.

Table 2

Cronbach Alpha Test's Result on Reliability of Instrument

S/N	Dimensions/scale	Number of items	Alpha value
1	Niche marketing strategy	4	0.812
2	Interpersonal communication strategy	4	0.760
3	Paid advertisement strategy	4	0.880
4	Customer satisfaction		
5	Sales growth	4	0.865
Total		20	

Source: Desk Research (2023).

Thus, from the analyses, on table 2, the results showed a reliability score above 0.7 which implies that the study used a reliable instrument.

Data Analysis and Results

The data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistic with aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The result was interpreted and discussed to provide answers to the research questions.

Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval Analysis

Both useful and abandoned copies of the questionnaire were recorded. The study analyzed the questionnaire issued and the percentage of copies retrieved for analyses. The result shows that a total of 233 (100%) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the fifteen (15) Beverage firms in Rivers State. The number of useful copies obtained was 224 (96.1%), while the abandoned copies were 9 (3.9%). This result indicates that a huge number of respondents participated in providing data for this study. This also shows success in questionnaire administration. The study used simple regression statistics to test the association between the independent variables (intrapreneurship marketing strategies) and dependent variables (business success). A total of 233 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. Out of this number, 224 were duly filled out and retrieved for analysis. This shows that a greater number of participants participated in generating responses to the items on the questionnaire. Table 1 provides the results of the mean score and standard deviation.

Table 3

Provides the Result of the Means score and Standard Deviations.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Niche marketing strategy	4.3384	1.50278	224
Paid advertising strategy	4.3907	1.62812	224
Interpersonal communication strategy	3.4012	1.86288	224
Customer satisfaction	3.3907	1.62812	224
Business success			

Source: Desk Research (2023).

The result in Table 3 shows that all variables achieved a mean score of 3.0 or above, showing that the participants actually attempted to provide positive responses to the items of the variables.

Test of Hypotheses

The stated null statements of hypotheses were tested in this section in order to ascertain the association between each pair of the independent and dependent variables. The result will enable the generation of findings for the study. Table 4 contained the results of the hypotheses tested

Table 4
Correlation Coefficients between the Variables

		Correlations				
		Niche marketing strategy	Interperson al communicat ion strategy	Paid advertisem ent strategy	Customer satisfaction	Sales growth
Niche marketing strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	.642**	.574**	.545**	.657**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Interpersonal communication strategy	Pearson Correlation	.642**	1	.585**	.554**	.540**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Paid advertisement strategy	Pearson Correlation	.574**	.585**	1	.504**	.620**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.545**	.554**	.504**	1	.578**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	224	224	224	224	224
Sales growth	Pearson Correlation	.657**	.540**	.620**	.578**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	224	224	224	224	224

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Desk Research (2023).

The result in Table 4 revealed that niche marketing strategy is associated with customer satisfaction at 0.545 when $P_v = 000 < 0.01$. Hence, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between niche marketing strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State. This implies that beverage firms that adopt niche marketing strategies are more likely to satisfy their customers compared to those that do not.

With respect to tested hypotheses 2, Table 4 also shows that niche marketing strategy is associated with customer satisfaction at 0.657 when $P_v = 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between paid advertising strategy and sales growth of beverage firms in Rivers State. This implies that when beverage firms effectively implement niche marketing

strategies tailored to specific customer segments, it positively influences customer satisfaction.

Also, with respect to tested hypotheses 3 in Table 4 shows that paid advertising strategy is associated with customer satisfaction at 0.758 when $P_v = 0.000 < 0.01$, therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between paid advertising strategy and customer satisfaction of Beverage firms in Rivers State. This implies that Beverage firms that use effective paid advertising strategies are more likely to satisfy their customers, enhanced brand perception: improved customer engagement: enhanced customer loyalty: customer feedback ensures customer retention. This can contribute to long-term success and profitability for beverage firms.

Concerning the tested hypotheses 4 in Table 4 shows that paid advertising strategy is associated with sales growth at 0.657 when $P_v = 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between paid advertising strategy and sales growth of beverage firms in Rivers State. This implies that allocating resources to well-planned and executed advertising campaigns can positively influence a company's sales performance because such advertisements enhance visibility market expansion, fosters competitive advantage, and improve content quality. This also implies that beverage firms need to continue to invest in and optimize their paid advertising efforts to enhance their competitiveness, expand their customer base, and drive sales growth. It also underscores the importance of a data-driven approach, continuous improvement, and resource allocation for advertising strategies.

The result in Table 4 with respect to tested hypotheses 5 shows that interpersonal communications strategy is associated with customer satisfaction at 0.657 when $P_v = 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between interpersonal communications marketing strategy and customer satisfaction of beverage firms in Rivers State. The study's results suggest that beverage firms can enhance customer satisfaction by implementing effective interpersonal communication strategies.

Finally, with respect to tested hypotheses in Table 4 shows that interpersonal communications strategy is associated with sales growth at 0.657 when $P_v = 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between interpersonal communications strategy and sales growth of beverage firms in Rivers State. This means that beverage firms can achieve increased sales growth by implementing effective interpersonal communication marketing strategies.

Discussion of Findings

Niche Marketing Strategy and Customer Satisfaction

The result of the first hypothesis revealed that niche marketing strategy associates with customer satisfaction. This offers opportunities for these firms to enhance their competitiveness, build customer loyalty, and stand out in the market by catering to the unique needs of their target niches. It also highlights the need for ongoing efforts to refine and optimize niche marketing strategies for maximum impact. Research by Kocak, Abimbola, and Ozalp (2013) supports this finding. They explored how niche marketing strategies

contribute to enhancing competitiveness and building customer loyalty. The study found that firms focusing on niche markets were able to differentiate themselves effectively, leading to higher levels of customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Niche Marketing Strategy associated with Sales Growth

With respect to tested hypothesis 2, also shows that niche marketing strategy associates with sales growth. This implies that when beverage firms effectively implement niche marketing strategies tailored to specific customer segments, it positively influences customer satisfaction. Research by Johnson and Ramaswamy (2004) support this claim. They examined how niche marketing strategies influence customer satisfaction. The study found that companies focusing on niche markets were able to better meet the specific needs and preferences of their target segments, leading to higher levels of sales growth compared to firms employing mass marketing approaches.

Paid Advertising Strategy and Customer Satisfaction

The result shows that paid advertising strategy associates with customer satisfaction. This implies that Beverage firms that use effective paid advertising strategies are more likely to satisfy their customers, enhanced brand perception: improved customer engagement: enhanced customer loyalty: customer feedback ensures customer retention. This can contribute to long-term success and profitability for beverage firms. Research by Vakratsas and Ambler (1999) investigated the effects of advertising on brand perception and customer satisfaction. Their study found that effective advertising campaigns can positively influence customer perceptions of brands and enhance overall satisfaction, leading to improved customer engagement and loyalty.

Paid Advertising Strategy associates with Sales Growth

The result also shows that paid advertising strategy is associated with sales growth. This implies that allocating resources to well-planned and executed advertising campaigns can positively influence a company's sales performance because such advertisements enhance visibility market expansion, fosters competitive advantage, and improve content quality. Research by Dahlen and Rosengren (2016) investigated the role of advertising in creating competitive advantage through superior content quality. Their study highlighted that effective advertising campaigns not only enhance brand differentiation but also improve content relevance and quality, which are crucial for attracting and retaining customers in competitive markets.

Interpersonal Communications Strategy associated with Customer Satisfaction

The result of hypotheses 5 shows that interpersonal communications strategy associates with customer satisfaction. The study's results suggest that beverage firms can enhance customer satisfaction by implementing effective interpersonal communication marketing strategies. This implies that maintaining strong communication with customers, managing the brand's reputation, and addressing customer concerns effectively can lead to higher levels of satisfaction. Research by Grewal et al. (2008) supports this finding. The Authors explored the impact of personalized communication on customer satisfaction. The study found that personalized interactions and communication efforts tailored to individual customer needs and preferences significantly contribute to higher levels of customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Interpersonal Communications Strategy and Sales growth

The result also shows that interpersonal communications strategy associates with sales growth. This implies that maintaining strong communication with customers, managing the brand's reputation, and addressing customer concerns effectively can positively influence the company's sales performance. A study by Keller and Lehmann (2006) supports this claim as it discussed the role of brand communication in driving sales effectiveness. The research highlighted that consistent and clear communication strategies, which include interpersonal interactions with customers, contribute to building brand loyalty and enhancing sales growth over time. Based on the above empirical studies that supports, this study assert that intrapreneurial marketing strategies strongly associate with business success of Beverage firms in Rivers State.

Conclusion

The implementation of intrapreneurial marketing strategies holds significant potential for enhancing the business success in terms of customer satisfaction and sales growth of Beverage firms in Rivers State. Hence, this study emphasized the importance of niche marketing strategies, paid advertising strategy and interpersonal communication strategies to improve customer satisfaction and sales growth. By adopting these strategies, Beverage firms can promote new product and service development, effectively target their desired market segments, build strong brands, leverage digital channels and e-commerce, foster customer satisfaction, loyalty to achieve business success.

Recommendations

1. Beverage firms should use niche marketing strategies by looking for untapped or underserved market segments that have distinct preferences or needs and seeking ways to satisfy them to achieve business success.
2. Beverage firms in Rivers State identify and target specific customer segments and tailor marketing messages and offerings to meet their unique needs and preferences and ultimately, drive customer satisfaction and sales growth.
3. Beverage firms should continue to invest in and optimize their paid advertising efforts by selecting the right advertising platforms, targeting the right audience, and crafting compelling ad content to improve customer satisfaction.
4. Beverage firms should consider investing in and optimizing their paid advertising efforts to enhance their competitiveness, expand their customer base, to drive sales growth.
5. Beverage firms should focus on strengthening interpersonal communication marketing strategies with an emphasis on customer-centric communication, transparency, consistency, and active engagement to achieve higher levels of customer satisfaction.
6. Beverage firms should leverage interpersonal communication marketing strategies through face-to-face approach, and consistent messaging for driving sales growth.

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APPENDIX 1

QUESTIONNAIRE ON INTRAPRENEURIAL MARKETING STRATEGIES AND BUSINESS SUCCESS OF BEVERAGE FIRMS IN RIVERS STATE

Instructions: Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree).

	Niche Marketing Strategy	SA 5	A 4	N 3	D 2	SD 1
	The marketing messages are tailored specifically to customers' interests and needs.					
	The products and services offered meet our unique requirements					
	We find the niche marketing efforts to be authentic and genuine.					
	The brand's niche marketing has made us more interested in exploring other offerings					
	Paid Advertising Marketing Strategy	SA 5	A 4	N 3	D 2	SD 1
	The advertisements conveyed a clear message about the product or service.					
	I took action (e.g., clicked, made a purchase) as a result of the advertisements.					
	The advertisements were well-designed and visually appealing.					
	The frequency of advertisements was appropriate (not too frequent or too rare).					
	Interpersonal communications Strategy	SA 5	A 4	N 3	D 2	SD 1
	The company effectively communicates its brand values and messages to customers.					
	Customers feel valued and appreciated due to the company's face-to-face communications practices.					
	Interpersonal communication has a positive impact on resolving customer issues promptly.					
	The company's interpersonal communication strategy contributes to building strong relationships with customers.					
	Customer Satisfaction	SA 5	A 4	N 3	D 2	SD 1
	Customers are satisfied with the level of responsiveness and accessibility of company representatives.					
	Customers demand more of our products/services.					
	Customers appreciate the value for money offered by our products/services.					
	Customers enjoy the ease of purchasing products/services from us.					

	Sales Growth	SA 5	A 4	N 3	D 2	SD 1
	Our company has experienced growth in sales over the past year.					
	The sales targets set by our company are achievable.					
	Our sales team is effectively trained and skilled.					
	Our sales strategies are aligned with market trends and customer preferences.					